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Report

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D4.1: Regional, National and International Fora Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

D4.1 is a report on the implementation and measurable impacts of the Regional Specialization Fora, Energy Strategy Symposium and Energy Transition Symposium, activities that actively disseminate the cross-cutting SALTOpower outcomes among industrial partners and other stakeholders, enhancing the development of a common policy alignment on MS technologies implementation for various processes at different political and geographical levels (Task 4.1, WP4).

Designed as measures to maximize SALTOpower's impact at the 4Helix level: Academia, Policy Makers, Industry, and Civil Society, these events foster the project's outreach at regional (Regional Specialization Fora), national (Energy Strategy Symposium) and international levels (Energy Transition Symposium), as taken from the perspective of the Widening partner: national and regional levels refer to the widening partner, UÉvora, thus referring to Portugal and the Alentejo region; the international level, on the other hand, allowed for the participation of stakeholders from the Consortium countries, implying the presence of participants from Portugal, Italy and Germany.

These events follow one of SALTOpower's objectives, 4. To enhance the networking of UEvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry.

2. REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION FORA

Aiming at the engagement of relevant, to SALTOpower's objectives, 4-Helix stakeholders at the regional level, the Regional Specialization Fora (RSF) was designed as a periodic event engaging Policy, Industry and Academia around the role of SALTOpower technological solutions in the objectives of the Regional Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3).

This event was foreseen to take place every 6 months, with a total of 5 events along the project, in M6, M12, M18, M24 and M30. Due to technical-administrative constraints, the first RSF was organised in M12, and 4 editions have already been held (RSF#4 was held together with the Energy Strategy Symposium to promote more participation of regional actors), being RSF#5 planned for September 2025 (M35).

With a first edition aimed at presenting the project scope and technological solutions, these Fora fostered a continued discussion, with the participants, on the potential of SALTOpower technologies for the region, the possible role of regional industry in their development and the potential impact of both technology use and production in the RIS3 and in the regional development strategy.

Though the audience kept rising from each RSF event, it became clear that there is a lack of regional stakeholders in SALTOpower's technological field. In fact, and being an essentially agrarian region, besides some industrial capabilities existing in the sole relevant industrial pole in the region - the petrochemical complex in Sines - present in the events after participation of some companies providing services at the hydraulics, welding or control areas, the level of success of these initiatives, when measured by the target audiences sought in the proposal, revealed to be modest.

Table 2.1 summarises the number of participants in the 4 RSF events and their level of success.

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

Table 2.1: Number of participants in RFS#1 to #4 and level of success (KPI)

Regional Specialization Forum	Level of Success	New external Registrations*	External participants registration**	Total registrations
RSF#1	Good: 15-25 registrations	3	3	7
RSF#2		5	7	15
RSF#3	Very Good: 26-40 registrations	3	4	15
RSF#4	Excellent: >40 registrations	6	7	19

* New external participants in each event

** Participants not affiliated with any of the SALTOpower Consortium partners

The distribution of external participants, in each of the RSF editions, by type of actor is presented in the graphic of Figure 2.1. The percentage distribution of actors in the 4 RSF editions already completed is presented in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.1: RSF audience by type of actor and RSF edition

Figure 2.2: Percentage distribution of actor types among the overall audience of the 4 RSF editions already completed

Both announcements and news about the RSF editions were published on SALTOpower communication channels (social media, newsletter and website, Figure 2.3), and the presentations are available on SALTOpower Zenodo and website: <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#presentations>.

Figure 2.3. RSF#1 announcement on SLTOpower LinkedIn

A description of each of the RSF editions follows.

2.1. RSF #1

The first edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 24th of October 2023 (M12), in the CCDR Alentejo (Regional Coordination and Development Commission) installations (Figure 2.1.1). With a total of 7 participants (3 external to the SALTOpower team, being one from the Industry and 2 from the Policy sector - Appendix 2), the event started with a presentation of SALTOpower and its technological solutions (thermochemical and Carnot batteries areas), as well as the relationship with EREI (Regional Strategy for Smart Specialisation) Alentejo 2030 and the regional potential.

Figure 2.1.1. RSF#1 (October 2023)

2.2. RSF #2

The second edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 18th of April 2024 (M18), in the CDR Alentejo (Regional Coordination and Development Commission) installations (Figure 2.2.1). With a total of 15 participants (7 external to the SALTOpower team, being 4 from the Industry and 5 new external participants - Appendix 2), the event started with a review of the molten salts technology, selling points, value chains and regional potential, and the SALTOpower infrastructure, activities and know-how.

Figure 2.2.1. RSF#2 (April 2024)

2.3. RSF #3

The third edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 21st of June 2024 (M19), in the auditorium of the University of Évora (Figure 2.3.3). With a total of 15 participants (4 external to the SALTOpower team, all from the Industry, and 3 were new participants regarding the previous editions - Appendix 2), the event started with an overview of the SALTOpower ongoing tasks and other ongoing projects related to the same technological topics. These participants were also invited to visit the UÉvora Research Infrastructure, in Herdade da Mitra, together with the Sol2H2O RSF#3 participants (as UÉvora coordinates both Horizon Europe Twinning Projects), and the XIX Iberian Congress and XV Ibero-American Congress on Solar Energy (CIES'24) participants, organised by UÉvora in the previous days.

Figure 2.3.3. RSF#3 (June 2024)

2.4. RSF #4

The fourth edition of RSF took place in Évora, on the 13th of February 2025 (M28), in Casa Cordovil, University of Évora (Figure 3.1.7), along with the Energy Strategy Symposium, a debate on the regional strategy was held. A total of 19 regional participants (7 external to the SALTOpower team, all from the Industry and 6 being new participants regarding the previous editions - Figure 2.4.1) were present in both events, which also included a visit to Herdade da Mitra to visit SALTOpower Research Infrastructure.

Figure 2.4.1. RSF#4 (February 2025)

2.5. RSF #5

The fifth edition of RSF will be organised in September 2025 (M35), along with the SALTOpower participation in the 3rd Energy and Water Innovation & Technology Trade Show (ENERH2O).

3. ENERGY STRATEGY SYMPOSIUM

The national Energy Strategy Symposium (ESSymp) was designed as an event “aiming at the presentation and discussion of the potential role of MS technologies in the objectives of the National Energy and Climate Plan, as well as of the potential for industrial development and

technology exports stemming from the application of the existing/developing Industrial capacity to the technological solutions sought in SALTOpower.[....]”.

Originally sought as a 2-days event, soon became clear that engaging 4-Helix actors to such a duration would not be easily achievable. Without compromising the objective and scope of the event, namely:

- the presentation of SALTOpower technological solutions;
- their role in the decarbonization objectives of both the National Energy and Climate Plan and the European 2050 Energy Roadmap objectives;
- National Industrial capacities;
- alternative R&I work, competitor technological concepts, regulatory environment and targeted markets;
- Presentations by both the SALTOpower Consortium, Policy and Industrial actors,

the event was shortened to a 1-day symposium organised on the 13th of February 2025 (M28), at the University of Évora.

Being a national symposium, the event was in Portuguese, exclusively onsite, and the presentations and discussion were not recorded, so as not to inhibit the participation.

The agenda, presented in Figure 3.2, included presentations on the SALTOpower team side, on:

- SALTOpower project;
- Molten Salt technologies;
- SALTOpower Beyond SoA concept;
- Competitiveness aspects;
- Related value chain coverage.

The agenda also included presentations from:

- Policy actors, Directorate General of Energy and Geology, framing SALTOpower technological solutions in the scope of the Portuguese National Energy and Climate Plan 2030;
- Civil Society actors, Portuguese Association of Renewable Energies, presenting market related aspects of SALTOpower technological solutions;
- Industry actors, with four different companies presenting their products and/or services in SALTOpower related fields.

One of the contents raising special attention among the audience was that related to the value chain coverage, at both regional and national levels, of SALTOpower Beyond SoA technologies, from which important conclusions could be drawn:

- at the regional level, SALTOpower related value chains can be covered by existing companies at a scarce 19% level regarding installation activities, at 40% regarding O&M activities, and no capabilities can be found at the manufacturing activities level;
- at the national level, these values rise to 53%, at manufacturing, and 100% at both installation and O&M levels.

This study rendered clear that an engagement of industrial actors around SALTOpower technological solutions is likely to benefit from a national scoped partnership, with most of the industrial capabilities being located in the northern (and more industrial) region of Portugal.

Following this conclusion and suggestions from the industrial actors in the audience, the organisation of a second national event, in Porto, is under discussion, possibly taking place in complementarity with SALTOpower’s presence in an Industrial Fair on Water and Energy in Porto, in late September.

Both announcements and news about the ESSymp were published on SALTOpower communication channels (social media, newsletter and website, Figure 3.3), and the authorised presentations are available on SALTOpower Zenodo and website: <https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#presentations>.

A press release was published to announce the ESSymp (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#in-the-media>).

Table 3.1 summarises the number of participants and the expected level of success.

Table 3.1: Number of participants in ESSymp and level of success (KPI)

	Level of Success	Registrations
Energy Strategy Symposium	Good: 15-25 registrations Very Good: 26-40 registrations Excellent: >40 registrations	Total: 33 External: 23

The 33 participants included: 23 external participants, being 2 from Policy, 2 from Academia, and 19 from Industry (Appendix 2). The percentage distribution of external participants, by type of actor is presented in the graphic of Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Percentage distribution of actor types among the audience of the ESSymp

SALTOpower ESSymp: Programa

13.02.2025		
09.15	Apresentação do projeto SALTOpower <i>SALTOpower project presentation</i>	Pedro Horta (UÉvora)
09.25	Sais fundidos: o quê, para quê, como? - SoA <i>Molten Salts: what, for what, how? - SoA</i>	Pedro Horta (UÉvora)
09.40	SoA e além do SoA - conceito e aplicações <i>SoA + beyond SoA - concept and applications</i>	Radia Ait El Cadi / Diogo Canavarro (UÉvora)
09.50	PNEC 2030 revisto <i>PNEC 2030 revised</i>	António Vasconcelos (DGEG)
10.20	Coffee break	
10.40	Potenciais aplicações adequadas ao PNEC 2030 <i>Potential applications suiting PNEC2030</i>	Pedro Horta (UÉvora)
11.00	Mercados <i>Markets</i>	Sara Freitas (APREN)
11.30	Competitividade <i>Competitiveness</i>	Tiago Eusébio / João Marchã (UÉvora)
11.45	Cadeia de valor <i>Value chain</i>	Tiago Eusébio / João Marchã (UÉvora)
12.00	Apresentação do projeto ATE <i>ATE project presentation</i>	Pedro Horta (UÉvora)
12.30	Almoço	
13.30	Apresentações de empresas <i>Company presentations</i>	Raul Bonito (Capwatt) Manuel da Rocha (SmartEnergy) David Pires (PLEXUS) Mário Ribeiro (ISQ)
14.30	Mesa redonda <i>Round-table</i>	Moderador: Pedro Horta
15.00	Visita técnica à Infraestrutura de Investigação da Universidade de Évora - EMSP <i>Technical visit to UÉvora Research Infrastructure</i>	autocarro <i>bus</i>
17.30	Fim	

Figure 3.2. ESSymp agenda

Energy Strategy Symposium

15/01/2024

The event will take place on February 13th in Évora

Figure 3.3. ESSymp announcement on SALTOpower website (News section)

The ESSymp included a visit to Herdade da Mitra, where the UÉvora Research Infrastructure is located (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4. ESSymp (February 2025)

After the symposium, a satisfaction survey was presented to the participants (by the end of the event, with a QR code and sent by email to allow further answers) and 7 answers were received (Appendix 3), that 57,1% of the participants who answered the survey were satisfied and 42,9% totally satisfied with the symposium (Figure 3.5), and that the ESSymp corresponded to their expectations (Figure 3.6). To the question “Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented? If so, to what extent?”, participants answered:

- *“The technological solutions presented undoubtedly aroused my interest, especially in their potential for use as batteries.”;*
- *“Yes, as soon as they reach commercial maturity (TRL9), making additional energy storage solutions available in the long term.”;*
- *“These are complementary solutions to those already in place for greater diversification of the national energy mix, with a strong boost from renewable energies”;*
- *“Thermal energy storage seems like a good alternative to lithium batteries.”;*
- *“Yes”;*
- *“Yes, but they need to be better publicised in the national industry.”;*
- *“Yes. Maybe not in the short term, but I liked some of the topics that were presented.”.*

Numa escala de 1 a 5, como classifica a sua satisfação geral com o Energy Strategy Symposium?

7 respostas

Figure 3.5. ESSymp Satisfaction survey (On a scale of 1 - totally unsatisfied to 5 - totally satisfied, how would you rate your overall satisfaction with the Energy Strategy Symposium?)

O Energy Strategy Symposium correspondeu às suas expetativas?
7 respostas

Figure 3.6. ESSymp Satisfaction survey (Did the Energy Strategy Symposium live up to your expectations?, where blue means “yes” and red means “no”)

4. ENERGY TRANSITION SYMPOSIUM

The Energy Transition Symposium (ETSymp) was a 2-day International Symposium covering Energy transition aspects: transformation of the Energy System, Environmental Impacts, Consumer Impacts or Societal Impacts – with invited speakers from Policy, Industry and Civil Society actors. The Symposium was held online in each of the three countries engaged in the Consortium, with the 1st day focused on the local discussion, and the 2nd day held online, with a summarised presentation of the discussion/conclusions in each country and a round table discussion engaging speakers from the three countries. SALTOpower Consortium brought to the Symposium their vision on the role of the technologies and research developed in the project and used the discussion/conclusions for a further alignment of the SALTOpower Exploitation Plan with the vision and needs of P.I.S. actors.

Following on from ESSymp, preparation began for ETSymp, taking place in two stages: a discussion at a national level in each of the consortium's member countries (Portugal, Italy and Germany) with a selected group of key players in this field, and a discussion at an international level to compare the results of the different talks.

After project meeting #5 in which the dates for ETSymp were pre-defined, the consortium partners, in online meetings, defined the methodology (with the support of Leonel Alegre, from UÉvora, that also prepared support documents with a script and instructions for all partners - Appendix 4 and 5), the dates and the questions to be asked of the participants on each national day, so that they would be the same on the country days and comparable.

Based on the 6-3-5 methodology, in which 6 participants write down 3 ideas within 5 minutes, in order to encourage a greater number of ideas, which can then be selected and discussed, it was decided to subscribe to the Miro online platform to be used in the sessions in the three countries. This platform allows participants to simultaneously write down ideas, simulating writing on sticky notes, without seeing what the others are writing, in the first phase, so that ideas are not influenced. Subsequently, the ideas were revealed and grouped, with the support of the participants, if they were repeated or similar, and a vote was taken on them, so that the 3 most important ideas were defined in response to each of the questions presented (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1. Example of idea voting on the Portuguese day, using Miro

These ETSymp events took place online, to allow the participation of relevant stakeholders who had already been present in Évora recently, in the case of the Portuguese Day, coming from different places in the country, and also because the final day will include participants from different countries. The presentations and discussion were not recorded, so as not to inhibit the participation.

For the Portuguese, Italian and German days, a small group of relevant stakeholders was invited, representing the 4Helix level of Academia, Policy makers, Industry and Civil Society. The Portuguese, Italian and German Day, all organised online, followed the same agenda:

- 1 hour - Introduction, participants' presentations and SALTOpower project presentation
- 2 hours + break - Idea production (5 questions, 3 ideas/question); idea clustering; idea classification (each participant has 3 votes to classify the 3 “best” ideas for each question)
- 30 minutes - Final discussion

The questions defined by the partners were:

1. TECHNOLOGY PERCEPTION
Which of the advantages of MS based multi-purpose storage are more relevant (you might indicate other advantages)?
2. MARKET REGULATION
How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of SALTOpower technological approach?
3. DEMONSTRATION
Which stakeholders should be cooperating on the development of a MW scale demonstrator of SALTOpower technological approach?
4. INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP
Which indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?
5. IMPACT (1 idea only/participant)
Please set up a one sentence statement on how you promote SALTOpower technological approach and its impact.

Invitations were sent to the selected participants by each consortium partner. The first day to be organised was the Portuguese day, after a Doodle was sent to the participants to select the best schedule. A Zoom link was sent for a session of around 4 hours, as defined agenda. The Italian and the German days were organised in a similar way, for the International Day, the scheduling was defined by the consortium before sending the invitations.

The agenda, the questions and the presentations were translated into each partner language in the case of Portugal and Italy, and kept in English in the case of Germany. The results produced are presented below.

Announcements about the ETSymp international day were published on SALTOpower communication channels (social media, newsletter and website), besides the invitations sent by email. News about the national days and international day were also published in SALTOpower communication channels (Figure 4.2), and the authorised presentations are available on SALTOpower Zenodo and website: <https://www.saltpower.uevora.pt/media/#presentations>.

Figure 4.2. News about ETSymp national and international days on the SALTOpower website

The national day events in each country stood for a voting audience as illustrated in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3. Voting participants, by country and by sector

4.1 Portuguese Day

The Portuguese Day was held online, on the 17th of April 2025, in Portuguese, with 11 participants, of whom 6 were voting participants (Table 4.1.1 and Figure 4.1.1).

Table 4.1.1: Portuguese Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	UÉvora (organisation/SALTOpower team)	-	●
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	DLR (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	UÉvora (organisation)	-	●
	UÉvora (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	Instituto Politécnico Portalegre	Academy	●
	APREN - Portuguese Association of Renewable Energies	Industry	●
	CapWatt	Industry	●
	DGEG - General Directorate of Energy and Geology	Policy Maker	●
	EFACEC	Industry	●
	CapWatt	Industry	●

Figure 4.1.1. ETSymp Portuguese Day

The meeting started with a presentation of the SALTOpower project, focusing on its objectives and impacts, clarifying the technological concept, competitiveness, TRL levels and value chain.

Each question was presented to the voting participants, and each participant could answer with two ideas to each question, using the “stick notes” on Miro, without seeing the ideas

Figure 4.1.3. The three most voted ideas answered in question 1.

Tables 4.1.2. to 4.1.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Miro in Appendix 6).

Table 4.1.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which of the advantages of MS based multi-purpose storage are more relevant (you might indicate other advantages)?	Multipurpose storage system: charge/discharge by heat and/or power	1
	Cost competitive for high temperature storage	2
	Reliability, lifetime	3
	Does not include critical materials	4
	Large quantities of stored energy	5
	Simplicity of the process	—
	In-house technology expertise	—
	Circularity of the fluid	—
	High thermal efficiency, long-term storage	

Table 4.1.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of SALTOpower technological approach?	Capacity market and ancillary services market	1
	Technology agnostic capacity auctions	2
	CfD contracts	3
	Economic support to large thermal energy consumers	3
	Power Purchase agreements	—
	Promote support lines for demonstration R&TD projects	—
	Non-price criteria (environmental, social impact and integration of the SEN)	—
	Hybridisation of plants (optimal use of the connection point)	-
	Adjusting network access tariffs for electrical energy	—
	Their exploitation as storage systems in CERS	—

Table 4.1.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which stakeholders should be cooperating on the development of an MW scale demonstrator of SALTOpower technological approach?	Component/technology manufacturer	1
	Heat offtaker	2
	Investor and/or EPC	3
	ANI	—
	Technological innovation centres	—

Table 4.1.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?	Technology costs in Europe	1
	Ratio Raw material quantity EU/World	2
	% technology (critical) materials with EU origin	3
	Volume of business/publications in storage	4
	Specific Economic Activity Code	—
	No. of patents/publications in storage	—
	No. of consumer companies involved	—
	No. of member states with suppliers for the system	—
	Ratio: number of European/non-European producers	—
	Quantity of stored energy	-

Table 4.1.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers
Please set up a one sentence statement on how you promote the SALTOpower technological approach and its impact.	Creating value to contribute to a new industrial sector and the energy transition
	SALTOpower where NEEDED
	An option to consider within the energy mix
	A LEAP (SALTO) in storage flexibility
	Alternative to lithium-ion storage, maximising its potential for integration into heat networks

4.2. Italian Day

The Italian Day was held online, on the 4th of June 2025, in Italian, with 10 participants, of whom 6 were voting participants (Table 4.2.1 and Figure 4.2.1), and following the same procedure as described in 4.1.

Table 4.2.1: Italian Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	•
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	•
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	•
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	•
	University of Firenze	Academy	•
	Politecnico di Milano	Academy	•
	University of Palermo	Academy	•
	Brembana&Rolle	Industry	•
	Magaldi Power	Industry	•
	Magaldi Power	Industry	•

Figure 4.2.1. ETSymp Italian Day

Tables 4.2.2. to 4.2.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Miro in Appendix 7).

Table 4.2.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which of the advantages of MS based multi-purpose storage are more relevant (you might	Multipurpose and flexible applications	1
	Robust, reliable and simple components	2

indicate other advantages)?	Continuous thermal feed to endothermal processes	3
	Environmental compatibility, non-flammability and low cost	—
	Easy integration with processes at different thermal levels	—
	Enhancing energy production during night hours	—
	Temperature modulability	

Table 4.2.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of the SALTOpower technological approach?	Incentives to decarbonised process heat	1
	Tax credits	2
	Value kWh.th as a function of temperature	3
	Remuneration of flexibility services	4
	Regulating overproduction from PV in summer (--> TES)	-

Table 4.2.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which stakeholders should be cooperating on the development of a MW scale demonstrator of SALTOpower technological approach?	End user (offtaker)	1
	Engineering	2
	Grid operator	3
	Universities and research institutions	—

Table 4.2.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain	LCOH	1
	Solar fraction	2

integration of different storage technologies?	Use of standard components	3
	LCOE	-
	Raw material availability	—

Table 4.2.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers
Please set up a one sentence statement on how you promote SALTOpower technological approach and its impact.	Promoting molten salt storage for new applications beyond CSP: supporting the flexibility and decarbonisation of the energy system, decarbonisation of the chemical industry
	Valuing all applications of TES (Power to heat, Heat to Power, etc.) because they are better than alternatives (biomass, H2), especially at high rates decarbonisation. Power to power less promising
	Keep process layouts unchanged and develop interface solutions. Disrupt the process as little as possible. Economic sustainability is central
	To have full-scale plant demonstrators operating within process specifications. This would support bankability.
	Considering that distributed applications are more promising, one has to start from the economic sustainability of medium-sized solutions to the sustainability of micro-generation

4.3. German Day

The German Day was held online, on the 6th of June 2025, in English, with 10 participants, of whom 5 were voting participants (Table 4.3.1 and Figure 4.3.1), and following the same procedure as described in 4.1.

Table 4.3.1: German Day participants list

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	ENEA (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	UÉvora (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	DLR (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	UÉvora (organisation)	-	●
	DLR (SALTOpower team)	Academy	●
	DLR	Academy	●
	DLR	Academy	●

Name	Institution	Sector	Voting participant
	TSK	Industry	●
	Glasspoint	Industry	●
	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	Academy	●

Figure 4.3.1. ETSymp German Day

Tables 4.3.2. to 4.3.6 summarise the results of the session (results from Miro in Appendix 8).

Table 4.3.2: Answers to question 1.

Question 1	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which of the advantages of MS based multi-purpose storage are more relevant (you might indicate other advantages)?	High TRL level	1
	Cost-efficient energy storage	2
	Simple/variable Integration	3
	Scalable up to multi MW-range	4
	Thermal transport + storage with same medium	—
	It relies on widely available non-critical materials	—
	High operation temperature	—

	High efficiency	—
	It's a safe technology	—
	Use of excess energy	—
	Non pressurised storage tanks	—

Table 4.3.3: Answers to question 2.

Question 2	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of SALTOpower technological approach?	CAPEX or OPEX incentives	1
	Value contribution of plants/ industry to grid stability	2
	Higher CO2 price	3
	Support high levels of process integration	—
	Specify the need for a certain storage unit together with new plants	—
	Simplified permitting and grid access	—
	Reduce or get rid of grid changes for this technology	—

Table 4.3.4: Answers to question 3.

Question 3	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)
Which stakeholders should be cooperating on the development of a MW scale demonstrator of SALTOpower technological approach?	Technology Provider/Developer	1
	Tech end user (operator)	2
	Public utilities	3
	Academia	—
	Energy end user	—
	Politicians	—

Table 4.3.5: Answers to question 4.

Question 4	Categories of answers	Voting outcome (1 = highest ranked)

Life cycle assessment	Life cycle assessment	1
	Life cycle assessment	2
	Life cycle assessment	3
	CO2 reduction	—
	CAPEX spendings by country	—
	Efficiency	—
	EU-raw material quote	—
	Number of European patents	—
	Supply security/resilience	—

Table 4.3.6: Answers to question 5.

Question 5	Categories of answers
Please set up a one sentence statement on how you promote SALTOpower technological approach and its impact.	It is sustainable Energy and provides independence from fossil fuels
	Choose the cost-efficient, environmentally benign technology that is designed and made in Europe!
	Support market introduction
	Build a demonstrator
	Molten Salt technologies turn renewable energy into a 24/7 solution
	Efficient energy storage with molten salts as storage and heat transfer medium
	SALTOpower helps to fulfil our emission reduction goals and future energy supply
	Key tech for a successful energy transition
	It's a key link between volatile renewable energy generation and customers energy load demands
	Ensures that energy provision remains reliable and affordable

4.4. International Day

The International Day was held online, on the 11th of June 2025, in English, with 45 participants (Figures 4.4.1 and 4.4.2), of whom 26 were external to the SALTOpower team, being 18 from the Industry, 2 from the Policy (Portugal) and 6 from the Academia/R&D institutions. Table 4.4.1 summarises the number of participants and the expected level of success.

Table 4.4.1: Number of participants in ETSymp and level of success (KPI)

	Level of Success	Registrations
Energy Transition Symposium	Good: 25-50 registrations Very Good: 51-75 registrations Excellent: >75 registrations	Total: 45 External: 26

The percentage distribution of external participants, by type of actor, is presented in the graphic of Figure 4.4.1.

Figure 4.4.1: Percentage distribution of actor types among the audience of the ETSymp

Figure 4.4.2. ETSymp International Day

The meeting started with the presentation of the SALTOpower project, focusing on its objectives and impacts, clarifying the technological concept, competitiveness, TRL levels and value chain.

A brief review of how the Portuguese, Italian and German days were held was presented, comparing the participants per sector, as shown in Figure 4.3. The most voted answers to each question, in each country day, were compared (Figures 4.4.3 to 4.4.8). After this, some companies presented their work in the field of SALTOpower technologies, with speakers from Siemens Energy, John Cockerill, and Brembana&Rolle, and a final discussion, resulting in relevant conclusions, was held.

1. TECHNOLOGY PERCEPTION			
<p>What are the three main advantages of this technology? (one idea per post it)</p>			
Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Multipurpose storage system: charge/discharge by heat and/or power <i>(Sistema de armazenamento multipurpose: carregamento calor ou eletricidade / descarga calor, combustíveis, eletricidade)</i>	Cost competitive for high temperature storage <i>(Custo competitivo para altas temperaturas)</i>	Reliability, lifetime <i>(Robustez, Fiabilidade, Vida útil Tolerância a picos)</i>
Italy	Multipurpose and flexible applications <i>(Flessibilità e molteplicità di applicazioni)</i>	Robust, reliable and simple components <i>(Robusto, affidabile e semplice (componentistica))</i>	Continuous thermal feed to endothermal processes <i>(Continuità di alimentazione termica al processo endotermico)</i>
Germany	High TRL level	Cost-efficient energy storage	Simple/variable Integration Scalable up to multi MW-range

Figure 4.4.4. ETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 1

2. MARKET REGULATION			
<p>How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of this technology? (write three ideas; one idea per post it)</p>			
Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Capacity market and ancillary services market <i>(Mercado de flexibilidade e ancillary services)</i>	Technology agnostic capacity auctions <i>(Competir em leilão (permitir um leilão "agnóstico")</i>	CfD contracts <i>(CfDs contratos por diferença)</i> Economic support to large thermal energy consumers <i>(Apoio económico para grandes consumidores de energia térmica)</i>
Italy	Incentives to decarbonized process heat <i>Incentivazione calore di processo decarbonizzato</i>	Tax credits <i>(Credito di accisa tipo credito di imposta)</i>	Value kWh_{th} as function of temperature <i>(Valorizzare il kWh termico in funzione dei livelli di temperatura delle utenze)</i> Remuneration of flexibility services <i>(Remunerazione servizi di flessibilità)</i>
Germany	CAPEX or OPEX incentives	Value contribution of plants/ industry to grid stability	Higher CO2 price

Figure 4.4.5. ETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 2

3. DEMONSTRATION

Which stakeholders should cooperate in the development of a MW-scale demonstrator of this technology?
(write three ideas; one idea per post it)

Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Component/technology manufacturer <i>(Indústria de componentes para o sistema)</i>	Heat offtaker <i>(consumidor de calor)</i>	Investor and/or EPC <i>(Investidor e promotor de sistemas de produção de Energia Renovável)</i>
Italy	End user (offtaker) <i>(Utente finale è il driver (occorre scegliere prodotti allineati alle esigenze))</i>	Engineering <i>(Partecipazione nella definizione/ progettazione degli impianti)</i>	Grid operator <i>(Rete: operatori di rete)</i>
Germany	Technology Provider/Developer	Tech end user (operator)	Public utilities

Figure 4.4.6. ETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 3

4. INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP

What indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?
(write three ideas; one idea per post it)

Answers by country	1st most voted	2nd most voted	3rd most voted
Portugal	Technology costs in Europe <i>(Preço da tecnologia na Europa)</i>	Ratio Raw material quantity EU/World <i>(Rácio Quantidade de matéria prima na Europa vs Mundo)</i>	% technology (critical) materials with EU origin <i>(% de materiais diferenciadores da tecnologia com origem europeia)</i>
Italy	LCOH	Solar fraction	Use of standard components <i>(Uso di componenti standard)</i>
Germany	Levelized cost modeling	Percentage of key components produced within EU	Life cycle assessment

Figure 4.4.7. ETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 4

5. IMPACT

In one sentence, how would you promote the impact of the SALTOpower technological approach?
(write just one sentence)

Answers by country					
Portugal	Criadora de valor para contributo para uma nova fileira industrial e para a transição energética	SALTOpower where NEEDED	Uma opção a considerar dentro do mix energético	Um SALTO de flexibilidade no armazenamento	Alternativa ao armazenamento por iões de lítio, maximizando o seu potencial de integração em redes de calor
Italy	Promuovere l'accumulo a sali fusi per nuove applicazioni oltre il CSP: supporto alla flessibilità e decarbonizzazione del sistema energetico, decarbonizzazione dell'industria chimica	Valorizzare tutte le applicazioni dei TES (Power to heat, Heat to Power, ecc) perché sono migliori delle alternative (biomasse, H2), soprattutto	Mantenere i layout dei processi invariati e sviluppare soluzioni di interfaccia. Perturbare il processo il meno possibile. Sostenibilità economica è centrale	Avere dimostratori di impianto su scala reale che funzionino rispettando le specifiche di processo. Questo supporterebbe la bancabilità.	Considerando che l'applicazione distribuita è più promettente, si deve partire dalla sostenibilità economica delle soluzioni di media taglia per arrivare alla sostenibilità della micro-

Answers by country					
Germany	It is sustainable Energy and provides independence from fossil fuels	Chose the cost-efficient, environmentally benign technology that is designed and made in Europe!	Support market introduction	Build a demonstrator	Molten Salt technologies turns renewable energy into a 24/7 solution
	Efficient energy storage with molten salts as storage and heat transfer medium	SALTOpower helps to fulfill our emission reduction goals and future energy supply	Key tech for a successful energy transition	It's a key link between volatile renewable energy generation and costumers energy load demands	Ensures that energy provision remains reliable and affordable

Figure 4.4.8. ETSymp International Day presentation - comparison of the most voted answers, by country, to question 5

In summary, the agenda was:

- Brief SALTOpower project presentation;
- What have we learned from the discussions held in Portugal, Italy, and Germany;
- Contribute to a joint vision on how to foster Molten Salt-based batteries and renewable fuels;
- Propose concrete collaborations: cooperation goals, R&D facilities and services, R&D needs, possible funding avenues;
- Become part of a technology developer/supplier community;
- Contributions to an action plan.

Following the discussion, the contributions to an action plan were collected (Figure 4.4.4):

Action Plan (follow-up actions)

Online, 11.06.2025

International Energy Transition Symposium 11.06.2025

Action Plan

- regulation: if you want to implement CB each steam generator > 1MW requires an approval process which might take 6 months, similar to fossil fuel based; no specific regulation to “green heat” → more interesting to move to larger sizes → work on regulations to streamline approval procedures
- **identify regulatory constraints**
- **simplify path to commercialization (B&R):**
 - attention of policy makers to this solution and need to streamline approval of these plants
 - facilitate reduction of LCOS by means of incentives (eg tax credit) and extended lifetime
 - european steering committee (R&D + engineering + manufacturers + end-users incl. grid): association to promote molten salt based technologies (regardless of application: CSP, CB, nuclear, Thermochem, utilities, Industry...)
- don't underestimate importance of R&D results and further development (clear pathway)

International Energy Transition Symposium 11.06.2025

Action Plan

- show it can be easily integrated in commercial applications
- follow-up to IEA Task on Energy Storage (bankability, technical viability) → Hi CBest: Power-to-Heat and Heat integrated Carnot Batteries for Zero-Carbon (industrial) Heat & Power supply
- look into EnergyNest demonstrator (concrete based, batch profile)
- suppliers database:
 - create directory of suppliers
 - create networking
 - possibly relate to association and/or IEA Task
- role of R&D funding:
 - demonstration as to show track record
- white paper on Thermal Energy Storage could save the EU over 500Mt CO₂ per year provides recommendations
- focus on end-user: they move if they see the right regulatory pathway, the proven solutions, the lower energy costs

Action Plan

- render visible the existing solutions to perceived technical problems (corrosion, freezing)
- focus on showing MS as a way to integrate energy vectors
- grid capacity is constraint: can CB be solution to alleviate grid constraints? increasing capacity factor
- people see benefit to offer grid services and go to li-ion: yet this market is limited
- decoupling MS from CSP as is restrictive, show examples? (eg NL Saltes builds small scale systems) <https://www.saltes.energy/>

Action Plan

- bankability
 - technical due-diligence
 - CSP projects have been funded on the base of specific CSP regulations and contracts (eg PPA), not on technical due-diligence of specific components → project finance
 - ability of the plant to deliver according to the planned
 - start by small plants, easier to finance, as to build up references and develop technical due diligence procedures
 - engage financial institutions on the base of these projects in the development of technical due diligence as to promote lower risk perception

Figure 4.4.4. ETSymp International Day conclusions: contributions to an Action Plan

After the symposium, a satisfaction survey was presented to the participants (by the end of the event, with a QR code and sent by email to allow further answers), and 14 answers were received (Appendix 9). Though the answers only represent a part of the participants, for instance, 40% of the attendants were from the Industry sector, but only 21,4% identified as being from the Industry answering the survey, the results show that 85,8% of the participants who answered the survey were satisfied or totally satisfied with the symposium (Figure 4.4.5), and that the ETSymp corresponded to their expectations (100%). Participants working in the three countries represented on the SALTOPower consortium attended (Portugal, Italy and Germany), which was one of the objectives (Figure 5.4.6) to have a more European view on the debate, but there were also participants who work in other European countries, and at list a non-EU participant has the survey answers showed (see Appendix 9).

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the SALTOpower ETSymp experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

14 respostas

Figure 4.4.5. ETSymp Satisfaction survey (overall satisfaction)

8. Country in which you work:

14 respostas

Figure 4.4.6. ETSymp Satisfaction survey (country)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Fostering SALTOpower's objective 4. "To enhance the networking of UEvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry", the Regional Specialization Fora, Energy Strategy Symposium and Energy Transition Symposium activities herein reported have been designed as measures to maximize SALTOpower's impact at the 4Helix level: Academia, Policy Makers, Industry, and Civil Society.

These events foster the project's outreach at regional (Regional Specialization Fora), national (Energy Strategy Symposium) and international levels (Energy Transition Symposium), as taken from the perspective of the Widening partner: national and regional levels refer to the widening partner, UÉvora, thus referring to Portugal and the Alentejo region; the international level, on the other hand, allowed for the participation of stakeholders from the Consortium countries, implying the presence of participants from Portugal, Italy and Germany.

Aiming at creating a vision on what could be a regional ecosystem enabling the development and deployment of SALTOpower related technological solutions, the four editions of the Regional Specialization Fora already organized (a last edition is pending to close to project end) have drawn the conclusion that, though some industrial know-how on related installation or O&M services exist in the region, stemming essentially from the

petrochemical pole in Sines, no manufacturing capabilities could be identified. This conclusion, aligned with the nature of the region's macroeconomic portrait - that of an essentially agricultural region.

Notwithstanding the adhesion gathered in the Fora editions, which can be considered "Good", with growing number of attendants from edition to edition and registering ever new attendants, this conclusion points to the **importance of establishing national wide approaches to the creation of an ecosystem prone to develop and deploy activities along SALTOpower related value chains.**

At the national level, the Energy Strategy Symposium gathered a total of 33 attendants, standing for a "Very Good" attendance level, and included in its scope:

- the presentation of SALTOpower technological solutions;
- their role in the decarbonization objectives of both the National Energy and Climate Plan and the European 2050 Energy Roadmap objectives;
- National Industrial capacities;
- alternative R&I work, competitor technological concepts, regulatory environment and targeted markets;
- Presentations by both the SALTOpower Consortium, Civil Society, Policy and Industrial actors.

One of the contents raising special attention among the audience was that related to the value chain coverage, at both regional and national levels, of SALTOpower Beyond SoA technologies, from which important conclusions could be drawn:

- at the regional level, SALTOpower related value chains can be covered by existing companies at a scarce 19% level regarding installation activities, at 40% regarding O&M activities, and no capabilities can be found at the manufacturing activities level;
- at the national level, these values rise to 53%, at manufacturing, and 100% at both installation and O&M levels.

In line with the conclusions drawn from the Regional Strategy Fora, this study rendered clear that an engagement of industrial actors around SALTOpower technological solutions is likely to benefit from a national scoped partnership, with most of the industrial capabilities being located in the northern (and more industrial) region of Portugal.

The satisfaction survey presented to the audience, after the Symposium, besides allowing us to conclude on the interest of this initiative, provided important feedback on the question "Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented? If so, to what extent?", to which participants' answers included:

- "The technological solutions presented undoubtedly aroused my interest, especially in their potential for use as batteries.";
- "Yes, as soon as they reach commercial maturity (TRL9), making additional energy storage solutions available in the long term.";
- "These are complementary solutions to those already in place for greater diversification of the national energy mix, with a strong boost from renewable energies";
- "Thermal energy storage seems like a good alternative to lithium batteries.";
- "Yes";
- "Yes, but they need to be better publicised in the national industry.";
- "Yes. Maybe not in the short term, but I liked some of the topics that were presented."

Both the value chain coverage related discussion and the aforementioned conclusions set the base for, and following the suggestions from the industrial actors in the audience, the organisation of a second national event, in Porto, is under discussion, possibly taking

place in complementarity with SALTOpower’s presence in an Industrial Fair on Water and Energy in Porto, in late September.

Finally, the international Energy Transition Symposium, built upon a common framework of discussion, in each of the Consortium countries, gathering a specific group of relevant stakeholders around five specific questions:

- TECHNOLOGY PERCEPTION: Which of the advantages of MS based multi-purpose storage are more relevant (you might indicate other advantages)?
- MARKET REGULATION: How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of SALTOpower technological approach?
- DEMONSTRATION: Which stakeholders should be cooperating on the development of a MW scale demonstrator of SALTOpower technological approach?
- INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP: Which indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?
- IMPACT: Please set up a one sentence statement on how you promote SALTOpower technological approach and its impact,

gathered a total of 45 attendants (26 of which external to SALTOpower Consortium), on that can be regarded as a “Good” result. Dominated by Industry stakeholders, this discussion enabled the Consortium not only to have a broad vision on the most relevant approaches to the challenges identified in the questions to the stakeholders, in each country, but also to draw a number of concrete actions for ensuing promotion of SALTOpower technological solutions and their market uptake.

These actions include:

- dissemination and higher visibility of ready available solutions;
- fostering bankability, including developing clear technical due diligence materials and procedures;
- draw a regulation simplification roadmap to ease the licensing and permitting of these technological solutions;
- promoting concrete incentive tools addressing these technologies, including both large capacity storage and green process heat frameworks;
- increasing the connection between research infrastructure and research results and the promotion of market regulation and market uptake actions,

with the general opinion that the creation of an European Association on Molten Salt technologies could be beneficial and a suitable instrument to implement these actions.

The results obtained in each of the events, showing a good adhesion by the corresponding target audiences, enabled SALTOpower Consortium to draw significant conclusions, to draw an action plan for ensuing actions and fully met SALTOpower’s objective 4. “To enhance the networking of UEvora in scientific and Industry fora, by means of disseminating the Widening RI services among Industry”.

6. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Communications Management Plan

The *Communications Management Plan* helps to ensure that all project stakeholders have the information they need to perform their roles throughout the project. It defines and documents the communication items' content, format, frequency, audience and expected results. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organization's drive, and this must be kept following internal organizational procedures.

I D	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Deliverables Acceptance Plan	Project Folder
5	Deliverables acceptance Checklist	Project Folder
6	Communications Management Plan	Project Folder
7	RSF folder	Project Folder
8	ESSymp folder	Project Folder
9	ETSymp folder	Project Folder

APPENDIX 2: ATTENDANCE LISTS

- **Regional Specialization Forum #1**

Lista de presenças Regional Specialization Forum #1¹

Nome	Instituição	E-mail	Pretende voltar a ser contactado?²	Subscrever SALTOpower Newsletter?³
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¹ Os dados que voluntariamente disponibilize são da responsabilidade da coordenação do projeto SALTOpower (investigador responsável: Dr. Pedro Horta) e serão armazenados, até final do projeto (2025), numa pasta de acesso restrito aos parceiros SALTOpower. Os contactos só serão partilhados exclusivamente aos parceiros SALTOpower (UEvora, DLR e ENEA) caso figure a sua autorização para o efeito. Este evento é público e serão recolhidas imagens.

² No âmbito da organização dos próximos eventos do SALTOpower, como as próximas edições do Regional Specialization Forum.

³ Se pretender deixar de constar na lista de contactos, contacte-nos para o e-mail saltopower@uevora.pt.

- **Regional Specialization Forum #2**
- **Regional Specialization Forum #3**
- **Energy Strategy Symposium**
- **Energy Transition Symposium - International Day**

APPENDIX 3: ESSYMP SATISFACTION SURVEY

Género

7 respostas

- Feminino
- Masculino
- Outro
- Prefiro não responder

Idade

7 respostas

- 18 - 30 anos
- 31 - 40
- 41 - 50
- 51 - 60
- > 60

Qual o seu setor?

7 respostas

- Universidade
- Organização de investigação e tecnologia pública
- Indústria
- Organização de investigação e tecnologia privada

Numa escala de 1 a 5, como classifica a sua satisfação geral com o Energy Strategy Symposium?

7 respostas

Vê um oportunidade nas soluções tecnológicas apresentadas?

Se sim, em que medida?

7 respostas

Indubitavelmente, as soluções tecnológicas apresentadas suscitaram o meu interesse, especialmente no potencial de utilização como baterias.

Sim, logo que atinjam a maturidade comercial (TRL9), disponibilizando soluções adicionais de armazenamento de energia a long prazo.

São soluções complementares às já existentes para uma maior diversificação do mix energético nacional, com forte impulso das energias renováveis

O armazenamento de energia térmica parece uma boa alternativa às baterias litio.

sim.

Sim, no entanto carecem de maior divulgação na Indústria nacional.

Sim. Talvez não a curto prazo, mas gostei de alguns tópicos que foram apresentados.

O Energy Strategy Symposium correspondeu às suas expetativas?

7 respostas

Tomei conhecimento de que os dados que voluntariamente e anonimamente disponibilizo são da responsabilidade da coordenação do projeto SALTOp... e DLR) caso figure a autorização para o efeito.
7 respostas

APPENDIX 4: ETSYMP IDEATION SCRIPT

SALTOpower - Ideation

SCRIPT

TECHNOLOGY PERCEPTION

What are the three main advantages of this technology?

1. Please write three advantages, one advantage per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes to answer.
2. Turn **private mode on**.
3. Start **5 min timer on**.
4. Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.
5. Present the ideas. Group similar answers.
6. Start **10 min timer on**.
7. Each participant must vote in the three favourite ideas. You have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting**. Adjust the voting area, if necessary.
9. **Drag the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board**.
10. Start **10 min timer on**.
11. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.

MARKET REGULATION

How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of this technology?

1. Please write three advantages, one advantage per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes to answer.
2. Turn **private mode on**.
3. Start **5 min timer on**.
4. Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.
5. Present the ideas. Group similar answers.
6. Start **10 min timer on**.
7. Each participant must vote in the three favourite ideas. You have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting**. Adjust the voting area, if necessary.
9. **Drag the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board**.
10. Start **10 min timer on**.
11. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.

15 minute break!!!

DEMONSTRATION

Which stakeholders should cooperate in the development of a MW-scale demonstrator of this technology?

1. Please write three advantages, one advantage per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes to answer.
2. Turn **private mode on**.
3. Start **5 min timer on**.

4. Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.
5. Present the ideas. Group similar answers.
6. **Start 10 min timer on.**
7. Each participant must vote in the three favourite ideas. You have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting.** Adjust the voting area, if necessary.
9. **Drag** the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board.
10. **Start 10 min timer on.**
11. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.

INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP

What indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?

1. Please write three advantages, one advantage per post it. To answer, drag a post it and write. You only have five minutes to answer.
2. Turn **private mode on.**
3. **Start 5 min timer on.**
4. Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.
5. Present the ideas. Group similar answers.
6. **Start 10 min timer on.**
7. Each participant must vote in the three favourite ideas. You have 5 min to vote.
8. **Start voting.** Adjust the voting area, if necessary.
9. **Drag** the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board.
10. **Start 10 min timer on.**
11. Discuss the three most voted ideas and rephrase, if necessary.

IMPACT

In one sentence, how would you promote the impact of the SALTOpower technological approach?

1. Please write one idea. You have five minutes do answer.
2. Turn **private mode on.**
3. **Start 5 min timer on.**
4. Turn **private mode off** to reveal the answers.
5. Group similar answers and discuss.
6. **Start 10 min timer on.**

APPENDIX 5: ETSYMP IDEATION INSTRUCTIONS

SALTOpower - Ideation instructions

EDITING

1. Open the Miro Board, following the links:

[English](#)

[Portuguese](#)

[German](#) (to be translated)

[Italian](#) (to be translated)

2. To edit the text, select the table or text box. On the menu, press and hold the locker to unlock the text box. Write your text.
3. After writing, select the table/text box and press the lock in the menu.

SHARING THE BOARD

1. Open the Miro Board, following the links:

[English](#)

[Portuguese](#)

[German](#) (to be translated)

[Italian](#) (to be translated)

2. Make sure that the board is Public. Go to [share](#) (top right). Select **can edit** in [copy guest link](#) and **editor** in [Anyone with the link](#).

Enter emails or invite from [Slack](#), [Google](#) or [Microsoft](#)

<https://miro.com/welcomeonb> Can edit ▾ [Copy guest link](#)

BOARD ACCESS

2 people invited [Manage access](#)

Uevora Team team (1) Editor ▾

Anyone with the link [Set password](#) | Editor ▾

[Copy board link](#) [Sharing settings](#) ⚙️

- To share the board, click [Copy board link](#) and paste to share.

ACCESSING THE BOARD

- When the participants open the link they will find the text box below. It is recommended that the participants write their names to identify themselves on the board, but it is optional. The participants write their name and press [continue](#).

- The participants don't have to write their email. They can just press [Enter board now](#).

INSTRUCTIONS AND TOOLS DURING THE DYNAMICS

1. Ask participants to go to board 1. **Technology perception.**
2. Read the question to the participants: *What are the three main advantages of this technology?*
3. Tell the participants that they must write **three ideas, each one in a different post it.**
4. Before the participants start answering, make sure the board is in private mode. Go to the tools menu on the top right (see below) and select Private mode. Select Go on private mode for all. Now, the participants can only read their own post its.

5. To answer, the participants must drag a post it to the white board and write on it. Before starting the dynamics, make sure they know how to do it.
6. Now, we will start. The participants have **5 min** to write their ideas. Start the 5 min timer (on the left of the board).
7. When the time is over, reveal the answers. Click in the closed-eye post it on the top right and press End for all and then Turn off for all. After 3 seconds all post its are shown.

8. Present the ideas and organize the post its by grouping similar answers. Stack the post-its with similar ideas, making sure they are perfectly aligned (otherwise, they will count more than once during the voting).
9. Each participant must vote in the best three ideas. Click on Open voting on the left of the board (3 votes; 5 min). Make sure that all post its are inside the voting area. If necessary, adjust the voting area by dragging the corners. Press start in the voting window.

10. Drag the three most voted ideas to the bottom part of the board. Discuss and rephrase, if necessary.
11. Repeat for questions 2 – 5.
12. The only difference is that, for questions 5, each participant will only give one answer and there is no voting.

APPENDIX 6: PORTUGUESE DAY RESULTS

SALTOpower

Abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower:
sistema de armazenamento multiuso em sais fundidos

1. PERCEÇÃO DA TECNOLOGIA

Indique três principais vantagens desta tecnologia.
(uma vantagem por post it)

Sticky stack

Resiliência

Timer 5 mins Start

Timer 10 mins Start

3 votes 5 mins Open voting

Custo competitivo para altas temperaturas

Simplicidade do processo

Grandes quantidades de energia armazenada

sistema de armazenamento multipurpose: carregamento calor ou electricidade / descarga calor, combustíveis, electricidade

Dominio da tecnologia in-house

Robustez

Não inclui materiais críticos

Eficiência térmica alta, armazenamento por longo período de tempo

Circularidade do fluido

Eficiência global do Processo

Escala

solução de descarbonização térmica alta temperatura

Vida útil longa e recurso a sais abundantes e recicláveis

Materiais não críticos

Potencial de despachabilidade em períodos de baixa geração renovável

Energia renovável

Aproveitamento de calor residual

Carga e descarga em térmico e elétrico

Carga e descarga despachável possíveis em simultâneo

Timer 10 mins Start

sistema de armazenamento multipurpose: carregamento calor ou electricidade / descarga calor, combustíveis, electricidade

Custo competitivo para altas temperaturas

Robustez
Fiabilidade
Vida útil
Tolerância a picos (3 votos)

Não inclui materiais críticos (2 votos)

Grandes quantidades de energia armazenada (1 voto)

SALTOpower

Abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower:

sistema de armazenamento multiuso em saís fundidos

2. REGULAÇÃO DE MERCADO

Sticky stack

De que forma a regulação do mercado de energia pode promover a adoção industrial desta tecnologia? (uma ideia por post it)

Timer
5 mins
Start

Timer
10 mins
Start

Voting BETA
1 votes 5 mins
Open voting

Competir em leilão (permitir um leilão "agnóstico")

Valorizando a sua flexibilidade

CFDs contratos por diferença

PPAs (power purchase agreements)

Apio económico para grandes consumidores de energia térmica

Incentivar financeiramente o investimento em soluções de armazenamento nacionais

Incentivar por meio de créditos fiscais investimentos que reduzam a utilização de gás natural.

Promover linhas de apoio a projetos de I&DT de demonstração

Mercado de flexibilidade e ancillary services

Incluir na legislação como uma alternativa

Critérios não preço (impacto ambiental, social e integração do SEN)

Promovendo mais a sua robustez

Pontuando mais a competitividade e autonomia Europeia

Hibridização de centrais (uso otimizado do ponto de ligação)

A sua exploração como sistemas armazenamento em CERS

Adequação das TARs (tarifas de acesso à rede) para energia elétrica

Redução ou adequação das tarifas que possa promover a adoção a esta tecnologia

Timer
10 mins
Start

Mercado de flexibilidade e ancillary services

Competir em leilão (permitir um leilão "agnóstico")

CFDs contratos por diferença (2 votos)

Apio económico para grandes consumidores de energia térmica (2 votos)

SALTOpower

Abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower:
sistema de armazenamento multiuso em sais fundidos

3. DEMONSTRAÇÃO

Que partes interessadas devem cooperar no desenvolvimento de um demonstrador à escala MW desta tecnologia?
(uma ideia por post it)

Timer
5 mins
Start

Timer
10 mins
Start

3 votes 5 mins
Open voting

Timer
10 mins
Start

SALTOpower

Abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower:
sistema de armazenamento multiuso em sais fundidos

4. LIDERANÇA INDUSTRIAL

Sticky stack

Que indicadores podemos utilizar para avaliar a integração europeia das cadeias de valor das diferentes tecnologias de armazenamento? (uma ideia por post it)

Timer
5 mins
Start

Timer
10 mins
Start

Voting
3 votes 5 mins
Open voting

- Preço da tecnologia na Europa
- CAE Especifico (se existir!)
- Volume de negócio / Investimento em Armazenamento
- Nº de patentes / publicações em armazenamento
- # de estados membros com fornecedores para o sistema
- Número de empresas consumidoras envolvidas
- Quantidade de energia armazenada
- Rácio: Quantidade de matéria prima na Europa VS Mundo
- Rácio: Nº de produtores europeus / não europeus
- % dos materiais diferenciadores da tecnologia com origem europeia

Euros por MWh

% de origem europeia no valor do sistema de armazenamento

LCoE

Custo do MWh armazenado

Comparar preços de tecnologia dentro e fora da Europa

Costs Learning Curve

Alternativa ao LCoE por ser mais holístico e menos específico aos conteúdos, é um indicador mais universal. Traz o grau de amadurecimento da tecnologia

Timer
10 mins
Start

Preço da tecnologia na Europa

Rácio: Quantidade de matéria prima na Europa VS Mundo

% dos materiais diferenciadores da tecnologia com origem europeia (3 v)

2

Volume de negócio na tecnologia ou Investimento em Armazenamento (2 v)

2

SALTOpower

Abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower:
sistema de armazenamento multiuso em sais fundidos

5. IMPACTO

Sticky stack

Numa frase, como promoveria o impacto da abordagem tecnológica SALTOpower? (apenas uma ideia)

Timer

10 mins

Start

Criadora de valor pelo contributo para uma nova filiera industrial e para a transição energética.

SALTOpower where NEEDED

Uma opção a considerar dentro do mix energético

Um SALTO de flexibilidade no armazenamento.

Alternativa ao armazenamento por iões de lítio, maximizando o seu potencial de integração em redes de calor

APPENDIX 7: ITALIAN DAY RESULTS

1. PERCEZIONE DELLA TECNOLOGIA

Quali sono i tre principali vantaggi di questa tecnologia?
(massimo tre idee; un'idea per post it)

Flessibilità e molteplicità di applicazioni

Compatibilità ambientale, non infiammabilità e basso costo

Robusto, affidabile e semplice (componentistica)

Continuità di alimentazione termica al processo endotermico

facile integrazione con processi a diversi livelli termici

Valorizzazione e produzione energia in orari notturni

Modulabilità della temperatura

Facile integrazione con sistemi ibridi

Materiale disponibile, non critico ed economico

Compatto: densità energetica

Hub energetico

Semplicità tecnologia

Scalabilità nella generazione distribuita (comunità energetiche)

Nella generazione distribuita grande compattezza (sostenibilità economica)

Flessibilità e molteplicità di applicazioni

Robusto, affidabile e semplice (componentistica)

Continuità di alimentazione termica al processo endotermico

2. REGOLAMENTAZIONE DEL MERCATO

Come può la regolamentazione del mercato energetico promuovere l'adozione industriale di questa tecnologia?
(massimo tre idee; un'idea per post it)

Incentivazione e calore di processo decarbonizzato

Valorizzare il kWh termico in funzione dei livelli di temperatura delle utenze

Remunerazione servizi di flessibilità

Credito di accisa tipo credito di imposta

Regolamentazione sovrapproduzione da PV in estate (--> TES)

Incentivazione e calore di processo decarbonizzato

Limite di temperatura max entro cui non usare gas

Incentivazione elettricità programmabile e (servizi dispacciamento)

Rivedere accise e oneri di rete

Incentivare la decarbonizzazione

Premiare il kWh reso disponibile quando questo ha un valore maggiore

Tenere conto non solo del costo, ma anche sicurezza e programmabilità

Incentivi su capex

3. DIMOSTRAZIONE

Quali soggetti dovrebbero collaborare allo sviluppo di un dimostratore su scala del MW di questa tecnologia?
(massimo tre idee; un'idea per post it)

Utente finale è il driver (occorre scegliere prodotti allineati alle esigenze)

Compartecipazione nella definizione/progettazione degli impianti

Rete: operatori di rete

4. DIREZIONE INDUSTRIALE

Quali indicatori possiamo utilizzare per valutare l'integrazione nella filiera produttiva europea delle diverse tecnologie di stoccaggio?
(massimo tre idee; un'idea per post it)

LCOH

Solar fraction

Uso di
componenti
standard

5. IMPATTO

In una frase, quale soluzione tecnica proporreste per consolidare l'accumulo termico come hub energetico?
(massimo un'idea)

Promuovere l'accumulo a sali fusi per nuove applicazioni oltre il CSP: supporto alla flessibilità e decarbonizzazione del sistema energetico, decarbonizzazione dell'industria chimica

Valorizzare tutte le applicazioni dei TES (Power to heat, Heat to Power, ecc) perché sono migliori delle alternative (biomasse, H2), soprattutto ad alti tassi di decarbonizzazione. Power to power meno promettente

Mantenere i layout dei processi invariati e sviluppare soluzioni di interfaccia. Perturbare il processo il meno possibile. Sostenibilità economica è centrale

Avere dimostratori di impianto su scala reale che funzionino rispettando le specifiche di processo. Questo supporterebbe la bancabilità.

Considerando che l'applicazione distribuita è più promettente, si deve partire dalla sostenibilità economica delle soluzioni di media taglia per arrivare alla sostenibilità della micro-generazione

APPENDIX 8: GERMAN DAY RESULTS

1. TECHNOLOGY PERCEPTION

Sticky stack

What are the three main advantages of this technology?
(one idea per post it)

same medium in the solar field and for storage

thermal transport + storage with same medium

It relies on widely available, non-critical materials

high operation temperature

high efficiency

It's a safe technology

use of excess energy

non pressurized storage tanks

proven technology (high TRL)

high temperature application range for power generation and industrial heat

cost effectiveness

easy to combine different sources and extractions

High temperature (up to 600°C)

Cheap and safe storage technology

Wide range of applications and compatible with different users/producers

Can provide constant power at constant temperature (easy to integrate)

High TRL level

Cost-efficient energy storage

Simple/variable integration

Scalable up to multi MW-range

2. MARKET REGULATION

Sticky stack

How can energy market regulation promote the industrial uptake of this technology?
(write three ideias; one idea per post it)

Long-term PPAs

Better incentives to provide control reserve

reward energy delivered from storage (i.e. at night, e.g.)

Incentivize flexibility even more

flexible market price - OPEX INCENTIVE

CAPEX OR OPEX INCENTIVES

funding scheme (bonus for storage) - CAPEX INCENTIVE

consider and incentive resilience

CAPEX OR OPEX INCENTIVES

promote life cycle assessments and reward emission free technologies

Funding for reduction of CO2 under LCA criteria

Consistent taxation of CO2

support high levels of process integration

higher CO2 price

specify the need for a certain storage size together with new plants

value contributions of plants&industries to grid stability

Simplified permitting and grid access

Reduce or get rid of grid charges for this technology

value contributions of plants&industries to grid stability

higher CO2 price

3. DEMONSTRATION

Sticky stack

Which stakeholders should cooperate in the development of a MW-scale demonstrator of this technology?
(write three ideas; one idea per post it)

4. INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP

Sticky stack

What indicators can we use to assess the EU value chain integration of different storage technologies?
(write three ideas; one idea per post it)

Levelized cost modelling

Percentage of key components produced within EU

Life cycle assessment

6

5. IMPACT

Sticky stack

In one sentence, how would you promote the impact of the SALTOpower technological approach?
(write just one sentence)

It is sustainable Energy and provides independence from fossil fuels

Chose the cost-efficient, environmentally friend technology that is designed and made in Europe!

support market introduction

Build a demonstrator

Molten Salt technologies turns renewable energy into a 24/7 solution

Efficient energy storage with molten salt as storage and heat transfer medium

SaltoPower helps to fulfill our emission reduction goals and future energy supply

Key tech for a successful energy transition

It's a key link between between volatile renewable energy generation and customers energy load demands

Ensures that energy provision remains reliable and affordable

Molten Salt Technologies are part of a future energy system for a reliable and sustainable energy supply with high fuel value creation

APPENDIX 9: ETSYMP SATISFACTION SURVEY

1. How did you hear about this event?

14 respostas

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the SALTOpower ETSymp experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

14 respostas

3. Do you see an opportunity in the technological solutions presented?

If so, to what extent?

8 respostas

yes

Power to Heat

Absolutely. However these solutions may have strong constraints to Energy Intensive Industries.

Green heat to decarbonize industry

carnot batteries

Certainly; industrial heat storage will become a lot more important with increasing industrial electrification.

definitely areas of collaboration possible, however, more discussion needed

4. Did the Energy Transition Symposium match your expectations?

14 respostas

4.1. If you answered 'no' to the previous question, tell us why:

0 respostas

Ainda não existem respostas a esta pergunta.

5. Gender:

14 respostas

6. Age:

14 respostas

7. Sector:
14 respostas

- University
- Public research and technology organization
- Industry
- Private research and technology organization
- Other

8. Country in which you work:
14 respostas

- Germany
- Italy
- Portugal
- Other

8.1 if you answered 'another country', please indicate which one:

5 respostas

Belgium
Algeria
Netherlands
Denmark
spain

9. Do you have any suggestions?

5 respostas

- no
- None
- 1) replace fully oral presentations by powerpoint presentations
2) I expected more technical detail and market experience information; maybe that can be added?
3) Molten salt is only one of the high temperature heat storage technologies. It would be good to compare molten salt to other technologies and to indicate where molten salt has a competitive advantage compared to other storage technologies.
4) Maybe good to add more information on how molten salt heat storage can play a role in the current grid capacity constraints.
- more engagement with end users including C+I; ensuring training is still available for this technology (e.g., steam technician)
- Dont underestimate the power of social media in regards du publicity

10. The data you voluntarily provide is the responsibility of the SALTOpower project coordinator (lead researcher: Dr. Pedro Horta) and will be store...o so. Images and sound will be taken at this event.

14 respostas

